

Patient perspectives on personalised medicine for obesity: An IMI2 SOPHIA Study

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ABSTRACT

Objective: Personalised medicine is seen as an exciting opportunity to improve the health outcomes of people with obesity. As research on phenotyping and personalised treatment for obesity rapidly advances, this study sought to understand patient preferences and perspectives on personalised medicine for obesity.

Methods: A participatory world café methodology was used to garner the perspectives of people living with obesity on the potential opportunities and limitations associated with a personalised approach to obesity risk identification and treatment. Data were recorded by participants on tablemats and analysed thematically using thematic analysis.

Results: Patients expressed the hope that personalised medicine for obesity would reduce stigma, support understanding of obesity as a disease, and improve treatment outcomes and acceptance. They also expressed concern about the accuracy of personalised medicine for obesity, its implications for insurance and that further advances in individual, personalised medicine, would detract attention from social, environmental, economic and psychological drivers of obesity.

Conclusions: This study highlights how patients are generally very optimistic about the potential for personalised obesity medicine but also raise a number of legitimate concerns that will be of interest to clinicians, industry, and policy makers.

Introduction

Personalised medicine offers new opportunities for the treatment of obesity. In contrast with current practices of evidence-based medicine that has resulted in a one-size-fits-all approach, personalised medicine takes into consideration individual variability in biological and environmental factors with the aim of predicting what works best, and for whom, when it comes to obesity treatment [1]. A personalised medicine approach to obesity represents a significant paradigm shift from obesity as a lifestyle or behavioural issue, to obesity as a set of complex, chronic and relapsing diseases worthy of the same consideration as any other life-threatening disease [2,3]. Often interchangeably referred to as precision medicine, personalised medicine for obesity seeks to determine distinguishable operational variables, such as phenotypic and omic

variables, by which a person's risk of developing certain obesity complications, and their likelihood of response to certain obesity treatments, can be established.

The perspectives and preferences of people living with obesity are critical to the development of effective personalised obesity medicine. Listening to, and understanding, patient perspectives, hopes and concerns should, as Ofri [4] points out, “be viewed as the single most important tool of medical care” (p. 221). This study seeks to establish patient perspectives on personalised obesity medicine.

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Methods

Participants and recruitment

The sample comprised of n = 25 people living with obesity (PwO) – 12 adult men and 13 adult women. Participants were recruited through an Irish hospital-based weight management clinic and represented various stages of the obesity treatment journey – from those making first contact with specialist services to those who have accessed a variety of support options over a number of years. In this way, we sought to capture a range of experiences and perspectives. In qualitative research, the quality of a sample is determined less by power calculation and more by the ‘theoretical sufficiency’ [5] of the data. This sufficiency is determined by the quality of the data collected – their richness, depth, diversity and complexity, what can be interpreted as data or sampling adequacy – rather than the quantity of data collected [5–7]. Additionally, qualitative samples are purposive, that is, selected by virtue of their capacity to provide richly-textured information, relevant to the phenomenon under investigation. As such, purposive sampling – as opposed to probability sampling employed in quantitative research – was used to recruit participants for this study on the bases that they are ‘information-rich’ cases. This sample is considered adequate for world café research but with the understanding that the views of any one sample of people living with obesity cannot, and will not, represent the views of all people living with obesity.

World café methodology

A world café methodology was employed to assess the perspectives of people living with obesity on the potential opportunities and limitations associated with a personalised approach to obesity risk identification and treatment. This methodology provides a forum for capturing patient voice and perspectives in response to specific questions while also promoting discussion, reflection and consensus building. Initially designed as a participatory method for citizen engagement and organisational change [8], the world café method has gained popularity as an effective method of co-production in qualitative research [9–11]. Brown and Issacs [8], the originators of the world café format, established the methodology at a meeting of academic leaders in California in 1995 and, following experimentation in several countries around the world, developed seven integrated design principles that guide the world café process. These are (1) set the context; (2) create hospitable space; (3) explore questions that matter; (4) encourage everyone’s contribution; (5) cross-pollinate and connect diverse perspectives; (6) listen together for patterns, insights, and deeper questions; and (7) harvest and share collective discoveries.

In this study, participants were welcomed to the research centre with tea and coffee and invited to sit at round tables spread out in a large room. Each table had six seats – five for participants and one for a research assistant whose role was to ensure participants recorded their responses on the ‘table mats’ laid on the table (Fig. 1). Following a general welcome and introduction, researchers set the context by providing an overview of the rationale and format for the world café. The world café was organised around two main research questions – with the questions, vignettes and wording piloted with the study’s patient advisory board in advance of data generation. The first of the study’s two research questions was introduced – both on screen and by a researcher carefully reading the question as shown in Fig. 2. Each question was preceded with a short orienting vignette. Care was taken not to elaborate or clarify at this stage to avoid leading or directing the round-table discussions. A set amount of time was allocated for discussion and participants were encouraged to record the essence of the discussion on the table mats using the markers and pens provided. The research assistant monitored time, encouraged contribution by all participants and ensured that quieter voices were heard and captured in the discussion. At the end of the allocated time period, participants were

Fig. 1. Sample table mat ‘predicting complications’.

Fig. 2. Sample table mat ‘personalised treatments’.

invited to indicate the statement/issue captured on their world café mats that they felt were most important by placing a dot beside the text. While not a measure of the importance of a specific point of discussion/issue, this allowed researchers to identify any convergence or consensus around the issues most important across a discussant group. Finally, a spokesperson for each group fed their group’s perspectives back to the larger room with a researcher making note of any comments or discussion that took place at this, whole-room, level. Following a brief break during which the table mats were replaced, this process was repeated using the second question (Fig. 2).

Ethics and consent

Ethical approval for this study was granted by UCD's Human Research Ethics Committee (HS-20-12-McGillicuddy). Participants were provided information and consent forms in advance of the world café and encouraged to contact the research team with any questions or concerns. These forms provided information about the study and the purpose of the world café and assured participants of their anonymity and right to non-participation at any stage. Signed consent forms were submitted by participants in advance of participation.

Data analysis

The world café table mats were transcribed verbatim and analysed using Braun and Clarke's [12] six-step framework for thematic analysis. This framework involved (a) becoming familiar with the data by reading and rereading the data in their entirety; (b) generating initial codes by jotting down descriptive labels and key words; (c) taking these initial codes and sorting them into potential themes; (d) reviewing and refining these prospective themes in terms of how accurately they reflected the meanings in the data; (e) further refining and defining these themes and what they revealed about participants perspectives in relation to the two research questions; and (f) formulating the findings as a 'whole' and presenting them as described below. In line with the participatory and collaborative nature of this research, once analysed and written up in report form, the data were presented to the study's Patient Advisory Board for comment and discussion after analysing and reporting. A meeting with the advisory board, once they had time to read the report, provided an opportunity to discuss the accuracy of the themes generated, their meaning, and the implications of these data for both obesity research and practice.

Results

Table 1 provides an overview of themes that emerged from analysis of data generated. These themes describe patient perspectives on personalised risk prediction and personalised treatment for obesity and are organised in terms of opportunities and concerns. These themes are elaborated upon in Table 2 and supplemented with verbatim responses recorded on the world café table mats.

Table 1

Patient perspectives on personalised obesity medicine: Overview of themes.

<p>Patient perspectives on personalised risk prediction</p> <p>Opportunities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduce stigma and increase understanding • Increase prevention and early intervention • Increased treatment acceptance • Increased acceptance of obesity as a disease <p>Concerns</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Concerns about accuracy and implications of test • Concerns that diagnostic test will place emphasis on biology and detract from broader factors • Concerns about insurance • Concerns about access to treatment/healthcare <p>Patient perspectives on personalised treatment</p> <p>Opportunities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Personalised treatment is empowering. • Personalised treatment would help reduce stigma. • Treatment would no longer be seen as shameful/the easy way out. <p>Concerns</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Is it really personalised? • Concerns about unequal access to personalised treatment. • Personalised treatment needs to include psychological treatment. • Personalised treatment needs to be long-term. • Need to tackle broader contributing factors (in addition to personalising treatment).

Personalised prediction of risk

The first section of the world café focused on patient perspectives on personalised risk prediction. The question was oriented with a vignette that suggested that, in five years' time, it will be possible to predict which of the 200 or so complications of obesity an individual is likely to develop. From here, patients were guided to discuss their perspectives on such a test (Fig. 2).

Patients expressed the hope that such a diagnostic test would reduce stigma and increase understanding. As one participant wrote, a test to predict an individual's obesity complications would be "more constructive – less moral/not a choice". They felt it would "allow [your] doctor to put you on the best treatment" and encourage increased treatment acceptance. Furthermore, patients felt that personalised risk prediction would support the recognition of obesity as a disease.

Concerns were raised, however, regarding the accuracy and implications of a diagnostic test to predict risk of obesity complications. Patients asked "is it accurate?" and wondered "if this isn't done well, will it undermine trust in healthcare further?". They also wondered if such a test would "take account of all factors? Mental health etc. not just biological factors". People living with obesity were also concerned about the implications of a test for personalised prediction of obesity complications for health and life insurance. As one participant put it, "[getting] travel insurance with diabetes [is] difficult. What would it be like if diagnosed with obesity?". Participants also articulated their fears that such a test was worth little without access to treatment afterwards and raised questions about cost and access to care.

Personalised obesity treatment

The second section of the world café again began with a vignette that suggested that, in five years' time, it will be possible to predict which obesity treatment is most likely to benefit an individual. From here, patients were guided to discuss their perspectives on personalised treatment for obesity.

Firstly, patients agreed that personalised approaches to obesity treatment were desirable. They felt that such an approach would be empowering, reduce stigma and challenge the view of obesity treatment as "the easy way out". As one participant wrote, "if you're given options, you are able to choose". This notion of choice, and the opportunities and

Table 2

Themes from thematic analysis of world café data with sample patient responses from world café table mats.

Patient perspectives on personalised treatment
<p>Opportunities</p> <p>Personalised treatment is empowering</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If you're given options you are able to choose • Regaining control - personalised plan. • If there are options then know options. • Gives you control and focus on your cause. <p>Personalised treatment would help reduce stigma</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Would change judgement. • Reduced stigma. Less about opinion. • Challenging stigma - unconscious bias me versus them. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • People around person might be more supportive. • Would reiterate it is a disease and not my fault! <p>Treatment would no longer be seen as shameful/the easy way out</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Remove the shame of getting treatment for obesity • If someone is diagnosed with cancer there is a plan. This would do the same for obesity. • It would no longer be the easy way out. • Nothing to be ashamed of - importance of helping other people know that there is nothing to be ashamed of. • People currently think treatment is bold/brash/ too much/ a bit extreme. <p>Concerns</p> <p>Is it really personalised?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Is it really personalised? • Doesn't it just come down to the same treatments? • What other plan is there? <p>Concerns about unequal access to personalised treatment</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plans should be affordable and accessible. • Access and affordability - must not exclude from access. • Equity of access to get personalised plans for obesity. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If you seek help and the door closes it is devastating. • Need to have access to treatment. <p>Personalised treatment needs to include psychological treatment</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Need psychological aspect dealt with • Need more psychology/ psychiatrist input. • Wider support structures also need to be committed to the plan including psychology. • Importance of psychological therapy CBT and education and prevention <p>Personalised treatment needs to be long-term</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Importance of continuous treatment, lifelong treatment. • Need to be given all the options. one treatment might not work forever. • Sustaining response to treatment is so important. <p>Need to tackle broader contributing factors (in addition to personalising treatment)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Will personalised diagnosis change or influence all the drivers of obesity e.g. socioeconomic/poverty/access? • Health policies really important in shaping our society and prevalence and treatment for obesity. • Reinvesting so important - circular investment so sugar tax put back into the health system. • Food industry - sugar - white gold. Impact on treatment - hidden in food.

empowerment it offered patients, was something that resonated throughout the room in the 'sharing collective discoveries' stage of the world café.

Patients expressed concern, however, about unequal access to personalised treatment and asked "is it really personalised?". As one participant wrote when asked to share their perspectives on personalised treatment plans "what other plan is there?". Patients also strongly expressed the opinion that any personalised approach to obesity treatment must include psychological support and that access to treatment needs to be long term – not just a one-off, short-term, intervention. Finally, patients felt that, while they were very positively disposed towards personalised approaches to obesity medicine, it ought not to detract from broader policy and population approaches to obesity prevention and management.

Discussion

This is the first study, to our knowledge, of patient perspectives on personalised medicine for obesity. Personalised medicine represents the future of individualised healthcare and expectations are high for the promise of personalised medicine in preventing and treating disease [13]. Obesity is no exception and it is expected that a personalised approach to obesity treatment will help an individual obtain maximally effective and durable weight loss results [14]. What is missing from the rapidly proliferating body of research on phenotyping and personalised treatment for obesity, is the patient perspective. This study captures and represents the perspectives of people living with obesity on personalised medicine for this disease.

The results offer a clear insight into the hopes and concerns of people living with obesity regarding personalised medicine. This insight will

inform scientists, practitioners, policy makers and remuneration experts' efforts to introduce a more personalised approach to obesity risk identification treatment.

Patients identified a number of fears or concerns regarding obesity treatment. They were concerned about the feasibility and accuracy of personalised medicine for obesity and feared being “let down by healthcare” if a personalised approach proved ineffective. People living with obesity are not unfamiliar with being ‘let down’ by healthcare. A systematic review of the experience of people living with obesity highlighted the negative experience many patients have when trying to access healthcare [15]. These negative experiences ranged from lack of respect to verbal insults, unmet healthcare needs and breaches of dignity. Research highlights how negative experiences deter people living with obesity from accessing healthcare which leads to greater levels of unmet healthcare needs amongst this group [16–18]. Further, many of those who have successfully accessed treatment for their obesity find that they regained weight after the treatment which, in itself, was a source of shame and silence amidst social and institutional narratives of successful weight loss and management [19]. It is unsurprising therefore that people living with obesity would fear being ‘let down’ by this latest advancement in obesity medicine.

The impact of personalised medicine on insurance was also a concern for people living with obesity. As one participant questioned “would insurance companies not insure based on outcome of test?”. Patient concern regarding the implications of tests to determine obesity risk and response, and particularly their likelihood of developing complications such as diabetes, on health, travel and life insurance is not unwarranted. In Ireland, for example, people with Type 2 diabetes can expect to pay, on average, 50–200 % more on their health insurance premium, while those with Type 1 diabetes pay, on average, 150–350 % more [20]. The management of data and the implications of personalised medicine for obesity on insurance requires careful consideration in advance of the rollout of widespread personalised risk identification and treatment for obesity.

Patients also expressed concerns about the purpose of personalised medicine in an over-subscribed and under resourced healthcare landscape. As one participant stated “what is the benefit of diagnostic test for risk [there is] no treatment or prevention?”. They felt that innovations in personalised medicine, if not available to all, would only serve to reinforce and widen existing inequalities in healthcare access. Disparities in access and quality of obesity care worsen inequities and outcomes for vulnerable and marginalised populations [21] and, without parity of access, personalised obesity medicine, may only add to these disparities. Furthermore, patients expressed concern that increased focus on the individual would reduce the parity of investment and attention offered to public and population approaches to obesity. They highlighted that “people don’t always want to be medicalised” and questioned whether personalised medicine will “change or influence all the drivers of obesity e.g. socioeconomic/poverty/access?”. While advances in obesity treatment based on personalisation and phenotyping may lead to improved outcomes for people living with obesity, it is clear that people living with obesity fear that personalised obesity medicine alone will not be sufficient to treat this complex disease. In addition to attending to factors such as poverty, inequality and healthcare access, participants reinforced the importance of psychological therapy as part of a personalised treatment approach. People living with obesity who participated in this study also voiced concern about the duration and suggested that obesity medicine, personalised or otherwise, needs to be long term as “one treatment might not work forever”.

Patients were, however, generally very positive and optimistic about a personalised approach to obesity medicine. They reported that personalised medicine would help alleviate the stigma associated with the disease. As one participant put it, personalised medicine makes obesity “less moral”. Obesity remains a highly stigmatised disease [22] and deeply ingrained cultural stigma, compounded by a lack of knowledge of the causes and implications of obesity, has resulted in widespread bias in

the medical profession [23]. Such bias affect clinician perception and decision-making [24] and stigma, more generally, “threatens health, generates health disparities, and interferes with effective obesity intervention efforts”[25]. This study reveals the potential for personalised medicine to reduce the stigma associated with obesity through increased understanding of the causes and implications of obesity as a disease. Patients felt that this increased understanding and personalised approach to obesity risks and treatment, reduces any tendency to revert to stigma and shame as a means of motivating behaviour change. Furthermore, the increased knowledge provides patients with options. This was considered of utmost importance for people living with obesity.

Providing a number of management options for obesity, as one person put it, it “gives you control and focus on your cause” and offered the potential of “regaining control” over their own health and healthcare. Adding to this positive development, people living with obesity felt that personalised medicine may also encourage others to seek help for their disease. It would “remove the shame of getting treatment for obesity” and place obesity treatment on a par with treatment for other diseases such as cancer: “if someone is diagnosed with cancer, there is a plan. This would do the same for obesity”. In addition to improving help-seeking behaviours by reducing the stigma and shame, personalised obesity medicine would, from the perspective of patients, improve patient engagement with treatment. It “allows you to approach things differently. I can now take the help”. In increasing treatment acceptance, and reducing the stigma associated with obesity, personalised medicine for obesity has the potential to address two of the most significant barriers to healthcare for people living with obesity: treatment acceptance and stigma.

A strength of the study is the novel world café methodology which represents a uniquely democratic and participatory approach to garnering patient insights and perspectives. The deliberative and reflective nature of the world café methodology allowed all participants to listen as well as share; consider as well as discuss; and for ‘quieter’ voices to be heard amongst the voices of those with stronger opinions and influence. The methodology enabled the implications of personalised medicine for obesity to be considered at every level – from the perspective of patients accessing specialised healthcare for obesity for the first time to those who have been attending a weight management clinic for many years. By engaging the study’s Patient Advisory Board in the final, post-analysis, stages of the research, as well as in the design and data generation, the study ensured that patient voice and preferences were integrated at every stage of the research lifecycle. As such, this study is unique in its emphasis on truly participatory knowledge generation – knowledge that will enrich efforts to optimise and integrate personalised medicine approaches to obesity.

Conclusion

Personalised medicine offers new opportunities for the treatment of obesity. In contrast with the current practice of evidence-based medicine for obesity that has resulted in a one-size-fits-all approach, personalised medicine takes into consideration individual variability in biological and environmental factors with the aim of predicting what works best, and for whom, when it comes to obesity treatment. As this study highlights, patients are generally very optimistic about the potential for personalised obesity medicine. They feel it will reduce the stigma associated with obesity and increase the number of people willing to seek to treatment for the disease. People living with obesity also felt that personalised medicine had the potential to empower patients to be more actively informed and engaged in their own treatment – a potential they felt particularly hopeful about given the stigma, judgement and blame often levied against people with obesity in healthcare settings. This study highlights a number of important concerns however, namely accuracy of precision medicine for obesity and its implications for treatment access and life assurance and insurance for people living with obesity. As research into personalised medicine for obesity advances,

these legitimate concerns warrant consideration by researchers, clinicians and policy makers alike.

Ethical Statement

I have read and have abided by the statement of ethical standards for manuscripts submitted to the Obesity Research & Clinical Practice.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Deirdre McGillicuddy: Funding acquisition, Methodology, Project administration, Writing – review & editing. **Joseph Nadglowski:** Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Project administration, Writing – review & editing. **Eva Hollmann:** Data curation, Investigation, Project administration, Writing – review & editing. **Carel W le Roux:** Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Methodology, Project administration, Supervision. **Emma Farrell:** Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Methodology, Project administration, Resources, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of Competing Interest

Carel le Roux has served on advisory boards for Novo Nordisk, GI Dynamics, Keyron, Sanofi, Boehringer Ingelheim, Herbalife, Johnson and Johnson, whilst receiving grant funding from Science Foundation Ireland, The Health Research Board and the Irish Research Council. The other authors have no conflicts of interest to report.

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Disclosure Statement

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Appendix

SOPHIA World Café

Format and session prompts

Question 1: Predicting Complications (Hour 1)

Based on SOPHIA research findings we expect to be able to predict, in five years time, which of the 200 complications of obesity a person will develop. For example, your doctor, based on tests, will be able to tell you if, and when, you will develop diabetes or osteo-arthritis. They will be able to predict if this is your highest weight (stable) or if your weight will continue to rise (progressive).

If we can predict the complications of obesity that you may specifically have

Q1. Do you think a diagnostic test would be helpful for the treatment

of obesity? If so, why? If not, why not?

Q2. Would that change the way you think of the disease of obesity? If so, how?

Q3. Would that change the way other people think of the disease of obesity? If so, how?

Question 2: Personalised Treatment (Hour 2)

Based on SOPHIA research findings we expect to be able to predict, in five years time, which obesity treatment is most likely to benefit an individual. For example, based on biological or psychological testing, your doctor will be able to predict if you will respond to nutrition therapy, medical therapy, or surgical therapy. They will be able to tell you which treatment will be most effective in treating your obesity and its degree of effectiveness (e.g. Medication is the most effective treatment for you and you can expect 30 % weight loss as a result).

If we can offer a personalised treatment plan which identifies potentially best treatment response based on tests

Q1. Do you think a personalised treatment plan would be helpful for the treatment of obesity? If so, why? If not, why not?

Q2. Would that change the way you think of the disease of obesity? If so, how?

Q3. Would that change the way other people think of the disease of obesity? If so, how?

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